

Cross-Sectional Analysis of Hydration Status and Its Effects on Cognitive Performance in Young Adults

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Abstract:

Background: Hydration is crucial for cognitive function and general health, but less is known about how it affects cognition, especially in young adults. Under hydration has been proven to impair memory, attention, and executive function. However, many complex ways hydration status affects these processes in youth are unknown. We must understand these effects to design tailored hydration methods to boost cognitive performance and well-being.

Method: In this cross-sectional study, 125 young adults (mean age 23.4 years) were assessed for hydration and cognition. Blood biomarkers and urine osmolality tested hydration, whereas the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test, Continuous Performance Test, and Stroop Test tested memory, attention, and executive function. Multiple regression and correlation analysis were utilised to study hydration and mental sharpness.

Results: According to mean urine osmolality, 40% of individuals were mildly to moderately dehydrated. Cognitive tests showed that under hydration impaired verbal and working memory. Hydration level had moderate negative relationships with Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test and Digit Span Test results. Hydrated people had better cognitive control on the Stroop Test, but attention tests were not statistically significant. Dehydrated people have lower memory, especially women. These findings emphasise the need of hydration for cognitive performance, notably memory.

Conclusion: Hydration is crucial for cognitive function, especially memory. The result supports earlier findings that hydration improves cognition. However, it highlights the need for more research on how hydration affects different cognitive domains and groups.

Keywords: Cognitive performance, Dehydration, Hydration status, Memory, Young adults.

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Introduction

Background Information

Hydration is essential to human health and regulates several physiological functions. Around 60% of the human body is water, which regulates body temperature, transports nutrition, and eliminates waste [1]. Water is essential for equilibrium, metabolism, and cellular function. [2] Study has also shown that water is essential to cognitive function and that moderate dehydration can impair mood, cognition, and performance.

Cognitive functioning includes attention, memory, and executive control [3]. Hydration appears to alter various cognitive functioning. Due to its impact on attention, working memory, and short-term memory, dehydration can reduce cognitive efficiency. Young adults who engage in rigorous intellectual and physical activities must understand the relationship between hydration and cognitive

performance [4]. Daily life and academic success require cognitive function.

Problem Statement

Despite growing evidence linking water to cognitive performance, young adult research are limited. Most of the prior research has been done on children and the elderly, so we don't know how water affects cognitive performance in this age group. Hydration status' effects on many aspects of young people's cognition are unknown. To maximise cognitive performance through adequate hydration, this gap must be addressed and effective guidelines and solutions developed.

Objective

- To determine if young adults are well-hydrated by testing urine osmolality and other indicators.

- To evaluations include memory, attention, and executive function.
- To determine if hydration affects mental acuity.

Hydration influences many physiological systems, including brain function, making it crucial to health.

We must understand water and cognitive performance to improve mental health and daily functioning. Dehydration's effects on attention, memory,

and executive functioning are the focus of this research review, which also fills knowledge gaps by [5].

Hydration and Cognitive Function

Hydration aids equilibrium and brain function. Since the brain is sensitive to fluid balance fluctuations, staying hydrated is crucial for cognitive performance. Short-term and long-term dehydration can impair memory, attention, and executive functioning, according to [6].

Figure 1: Hydration and Cognitive Function (Source: [7])

Memory

Water's brain impacts on memory have been studied most. [8] Found that dehydration severely impairs visual and working memory. Participants who experienced moderate dehydration (defined as a 2% drop in body weight due to fluid loss) performed better on visual and working memory tests than controls. A battery of cognitive tests, including visual memory and digit span, measured these effects. Our findings support [9], who reported that dehydration impairs memory, especially for complex processing tasks.

Attention

Dehydration also affects attention, or the ability to ignore unimportant stimuli. [10] Found that dehydrated people were more distracted and had lower reaction times. Low-hydration participants performed inadequately on response time and sustained attention assessments. [11] Observed that mild dehydration decreases attention and focus, as well as reaction speeds and accuracy.

Executive Functions

Executive processes like cognitive flexibility, problem-solving, and planning are linked to hydration. [12] Found that dehydration impairs executive functions and cognitive flexibility. The Wisconsin

Card Sorting Test and problem-solving were used to assess executive function. Performance and error rate were better for dehydrated subjects.

Mechanisms of Hydration Impact

Hydration affects cognitive performance through biochemical and physiological pathways. Dehydration alters blood flow, neurotransmitter activity, and electrolyte balance, affecting brain function. Dehydration reduces cerebral blood flow and increases stress hormone levels, which impairs cognitive function. Dehydration increases brain oxidative stress, which impairs cognition.

Factors Influencing Hydration-Cognition Relationship

The relationship between hydration and mental sharpness is complicated and varies. Gender, age, and exercise level moderate this connection. Age-related fluid balance and brain function alterations make older persons more susceptible to dehydration's cognitive impacts. Dehydration affects memory tasks more in women than men. Physically active adults may have less cognitive damage from dehydration because they can better maintain their fluid balance and adapt to fluid losses.

Recent Advances and Future Directions: Recent research has improved our understanding of the

hydration-cognition link by using different approaches and exploring new features. Dehydration changes brain network patterns and dynamics. Re-hydrating dehydrated people improved cognitive functioning.

Future longitudinal research should examine how hydration affects cognitive function over time and the mechanisms that produce it. Studying the impact of hydration on several cognitive domains in different populations, including those with medical diseases that affect hydration status, can provide a more complete picture of the hydration-cognition link. Individualised hydration methods and interventions that take into consideration each person's needs and attributes may help improve cognitive performance.

Methods

Study Design: This cross-sectional study examines how hydration affects young people's cognitive function. Cross-sectional studies are excellent for our research topic since we only need to test participants' hydration and cognitive ability once. This arrangement makes correlations easy to find and quickly assesses the population's hydration and cognitive performance.

Sample Size: The study will include 100-150 young adults.

Inclusion Criteria

- Age range: 18-30 years
- Generally healthy individuals with no chronic illnesses or significant health issues.
- No history of neurological or psychological disorders that could affect cognitive function.

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals with diagnosed medical conditions affecting hydration (e.g., diabetes, kidney disease).
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Individuals taking medications known to significantly affect hydration or cognitive function.

Data Collection: Hydration will be assessed by urine and blood tests. The urine samples will be analysed with an osmometer to estimate osmolality,

which measures solute content and provides an objective measure of hydration. Blood samples can measure hydration biomarkers such as serum salt and blood urea nitrogen. Working memory and verbal memory will be tested using the Digit Span Test and Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test. Cognitive control and attention will be assessed using the Stroop Test and CPT. Executive processes including cognitive flexibility and problem-solving will be measured with the WCST. Postings on campus, social media, and local centres will draw participants. We'll screen applicants to ensure they meet standards. Each participant will have a one- to two-hour test. Cognitive performance tests will follow blood and urine hydration assessments during this session. The study will follow ethical guidelines and obtain informed consent from all participants, ensuring anonymity and the ability to withdraw.

Statistical Analysis: The subjects' demographics, hydration, and cognitive performance will be described using descriptive statistics. The data distribution will determine whether we employ Pearson or Spearman correlation coefficients to explore the relationship between hydration state and cognitive function. This method helps explain statistically significant relationships between fluid intake and mental sharpness. We will also utilise multiple regression analysis to determine how hydration affects cognitive performance, taking into consideration age, gender, and exercise level. By removing confounding variables, we can better understand how hydration affects cognition. The statistical computing language R or the social science statistical software SPSS will be used to conduct these studies and accurately interpret the results.

Results

Descriptive Statistics: The study included 125 young people, 63 of whom were male and 62 female. Participants' ages ranged from 18 to 30 years, with a mean age of 23.4 years (± 2.5 years). Most participants (85%) were university students, with 15% working professionals. The sample included ethnic and socioeconomic diversity. Most healthy respondents reported no serious chronic illnesses or neurological issues.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Characteristic	Mean $\pm$ SD	Range
Age (years)	23.4 $\pm$ 2.5	18-30
Gender		
Male (%)	50.4	
Female (%)	49.6	
Occupation		
University Students (%)	85.0	
Employed Professionals (%)	15.0	

Hydration Status

Hydration state was determined by blood biomarkers and urine osmolality.

Sample urine osmolality ranged from mild to moderate dehydration, with a mean of 550 mOsm/kg ($\pm$ 80 mOsm/kg). According to blood

biomarker analysis, the average serum sodium level was 141 mmol/L ($\pm$ 3 mmol/L) and the average BUN level was 8.2 mg/dL ($\pm$ 1.5 mg/dL). Though within the normal range, these readings show that participants' hydration differed. Urine osmolality showed 40% of the sample was severely dehydrated, whereas 60% was well-hydrated.

Table 2: Hydration Status

Measurement	Mean $\pm$ SD	Range	Classification (%)
Urine Osmolality (mOsm/kg)	550 $\pm$ 80	400–750	Suboptimal: 40% Adequate: 60%
Serum Sodium (mmol/L)	141 $\pm$ 3	138–144	Normal
Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN) (mg/dL)	8.2 $\pm$ 1.5	6.0–12.0	Normal

Cognitive Performance

Cognitive performance was assessed with multiple tests. Average working memory capacity was measured at 15.3 ($\pm$ 2.8) on the Digit Span Test. Participants' Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test showed an average recall score of 25.4 ($\pm$ 4.1), indicating verbal memory ability. On the Continuous Performance Test (CPT), the average

score was 92% with $\pm$ 5% accurate answers. On the Stroop Test, which measures cognitive control, the average score was 40 seconds with $\pm$ 8 seconds completion time.

Participants demonstrated average executive function competence with a mean score of 40 ($\pm$ 6 categories) on the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (WCST).

Table 3: Cognitive Performance

Test	Mean $\pm$ SD	Range
Digit Span Test (score)	15.3 $\pm$ 2.8	10–22
Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test (total recall score)	25.4 $\pm$ 4.1	15–35
Continuous Performance Test (correct responses %)	92 $\pm$ 5	80–100
Stroop Test (completion time, seconds)	40 $\pm$ 8	30–60
Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (categories completed)	40 $\pm$ 6	30–50

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis revealed many links between hydration and cognitive performance. Lower hydration levels were connected to poorer working memory function, as seen by a negative correlation between urine osmolality and Digit Span Test results ($r = -0.35$, $p < 0.01$). The Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test found a negative correlation ($r = -0.30$, $p < 0.05$) between urine osmolality and recall scores, indicating that better hydration levels are associated with better verbal memory. Hydration did not affect CPT attention assessments ($r = -0.12$, $p = 0.30$). There was a significant inverse correlation between urine osmolality and Stroop Test completion time ($r = -0.28$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that better hydration leads to faster cognitive control.

Additional Findings

The Digit Span and Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Tests revealed significantly lower scores for dehydrated subjects ($p < 0.05$).

Attention and executive function evaluations were similar between hydration groups. Subgroup analysis showed that hydration had a stronger

effect on cognitive performance in females than males on memory tasks. Hydration state impacts verbal and working memory but not attention or cognitive control. Hydration levels affect distinct brain areas, emphasising the importance of being hydrated for optimal cognitive performance.

Discussion

This study demonstrated that hydration significantly affected young people's cognitive function. Working memory and verbal memory scores are moderately negatively correlated with urine osmolality, suggesting that dehydration causes poor cognitive performance. Our findings support previous research that dehydration impairs attention and memory. Mild dehydration affects cognitive tasks requiring complex processing and memory. This study revealed no correlation between dehydration and attention test performance, contrary to previous research. This may be due to various hydration thresholds or cognitive tests with variable sensitivity. The negative correlation between hydration and Stroop Test time complements previous research that shows hydration enhances executive performance. Well-hydrated people have faster cognitive control.

Table 4: Comparison of the Present Study with Existing Research

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings
Present Study	Cross-Sectional	125	Found that lower hydration levels, indicated by higher urine osmolality, are associated with poorer working and verbal memory. No significant impact on attention tasks.
Study 1 [13]	Experimental	40	Demonstrated that mild dehydration impaired cognitive tasks involving memory and complex processing. Significant effects on attention and working memory.
Study 2 [14]	Experimental	20	Showed that dehydration significantly affected cognitive performance, particularly tasks requiring sustained attention and working memory. Hydration improved cognitive functions in dehydrated individuals.
Study 3 [15]	Cross-Sectional	150	Found that inadequate hydration was associated with deficits in cognitive performance, including memory and attention. The study emphasized the cognitive benefits of adequate hydration.

The comparison table shows that this study's findings on mental performance and hydration match those of other studies. As Study 1 and Study 2 found, dehydration impairs working and verbal memory. Unlike earlier studies that found poor hydration affected attention Study 3, this study found no significant effects. This study supports the idea that being hydrated improves cognitive performance in general by highlighting subtle differences in cognitive domains and suggesting that the effect on attention may vary depending on the circumstances or measurement method.

Strengths and Limitations

This study excels at using objective hydration and cognitive performance measures. Blood markers and urine osmolality can be used to assess hydration without relying on self-reported data, which can be biased. Using well-established cognitive exams increases performance validity. Cross-sectional analysis is good for correlations but not causes and effects. The study only involved young individuals, so the results may not apply to other ages or health conditions. The study only employed one testing session, which may not be adequate to account for hydration and cognitive function changes over time. Because food consumption and physical exercise were not fully accounted for, residual confounding is possible.

Clinical Implications

According to the study, young people need adequate water to sustain cognitive function. Lack of hydration is strongly linked to poor working and verbal memory, thus public health guidelines should reflect this. Young individuals may benefit from learning how hydration influences cognition. This is especially true for brain-intensive students and workers. As advised, drink plenty of water and check hydration levels, especially during cognitive activity. Public health and educational campaigns should promote the mental health benefits of drinking enough water and provide daily suggestions.

Future Research

Based on these findings, future research should focus elsewhere. Longitudinal studies that track participants over time to assess how hydration habits affect cognitive function may help explain the association. Studies may also analyse how dehydration and rehydration influence cognitive areas to determine when hydration state affects performance. Investigating the pathways that link hydration and brain function may be helpful. Hydration's influence on brain function and neural processes could be studied. The hydration-cognition interaction may be better understood by include varied populations including individuals with chronic health issues or various age groups in the research. This would improve findings generalisability. Since this study adds to the data linking sufficient hydration to cognitive performance, more research and public health efforts are needed to promote hydration.

Conclusion

This study emphasises the importance of water on cognitive performance in young people. Higher urine osmolality is associated with poorer verbal and working memory. Our findings support earlier research showing dehydration impairs cognitive functions, particularly memory and complex processing. Hydration did not significantly affect attention tasks, but the study illuminates the intricate ways it affects various cognition areas. The study benefits from objective cognitive function and hydration assessments. Note that the study is cross-sectional and limited to one testing session. Staying hydrated is crucial for cognitive function, especially in high-intensity mental situations, and has major public health implications. Future research should examine how long-term hydration affects cognitive performance, what factors contribute to these benefits, and how to generalise these findings to diverse demographics.

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